

D9.1. Regulatory compliance monitoring plan and activities Part A

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About ThrombUS+

Deep vein thrombosis (DVT) is the formation of a blood clot within the deep veins, most commonly those of the lower limbs, causing obstruction of blood flow. In 50% of people with DVT, the clot eventually breaks off and travels to the lung to cause pulmonary embolism. Clinical assessment of DVT is notoriously unreliable because up to 2/3 of DVT episodes are clinically silent and patients are symptom free even when pulmonary embolism has developed. Early diagnosis of DVT is crucial and despite the progress made in ultrasound imaging and plethysmography techniques, there is a need for new methods to enable continuous monitoring DVT diagnosis at the point of care.

ThrombUS+ brings together an interdisciplinary team of industrial, technology, regulatory, social science and clinical trial experts to develop a novel wearable diagnostic device for point-of-care, operator free, continuous monitoring in patients with high DVT risk. The device will combine autonomous, AI driven DVT detection based on a novel wearable ultrasound hardware, impedance plethysmography and light reflection rheography for immediate detection of blood clot formation in the lower limb. Activity and other physiological measurements will be used to provide a continuous assessment of DVT risk and support DVT prevention via serious gaming. The aggregated data will drive an intelligence decision support unit that will provide accurate monitoring and alerts. Extended reality will be used to guide experts to design exercises and patients to use the device optimally.

ThrombUS+ is intended for use by postoperative patients in the ward, during long surgical operations, cancer patients or otherwise bedridden patients at home or in care units, and women during pregnancy and postpartum. ThrombUS+ will use big data sets for AI training collected in the project via 3 large scale clinical studies and will validate the outcome in the clinical setting via 1 early feasibility study and 1 multi-center clinical trial.

Deliverable D9.1 Description

Regulatory compliance monitoring plan. Output of Task 9.1.

Task 9.1. will implement the Conformity-by-Design approach developed in T.2.2 via: (1) Plan for product certifications for the European market. (2) Strategy development on how the specific regulatory approach could be to prepare the ThrombUS+ system for the EU market. (3) Drafting of a “CE roadmap” as a compliance guide for the project partners. (4) Training project partners via advanced workshops on compliance issues. (5) Preparation of new technical rules or standards should no adequate documents exist. (6) Accompanying the R&D work of the project partners to include regulatory requirements from the outset so that regulatory issues do not prevent later market access. (7) Accompanying the R&D work in the analysis of all specific general safety and performance requirements (GSPR), the selection of appropriate standards and the derivation of suitable testing and certification strategies. (8) Preparation, training or, if necessary, implementation of all required regulatory processes, e.g. quality management, usability engineering, software life cycle processes, clinical evaluation. Regulatory expert partner VDE leads this task. All partners participate to increase awareness on regulatory issues.

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Terms and Definitions

Term	Definition
CAMD	Competent Authorities for Medical Devices
DIN	German Institute for Standardisation
DKE	German Commission for Electrotechnical, Electronic & Information Technologies of DIN and VDE
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
EEA	Ethics External Advisor
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
EU	European Union
EUDAMED	European Database on Medical Devices
GA	General Assembly (when within the context of project management procedure)
HADEA	European Health and Digital Executive Agency
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
IG-NB	German Notified Bodies Alliance
IMDRF	International Medical Device Regulators Forum
ITU	International Telecommunication Union
MDCG	Medical Device Coordination Group (of EC)
MDR	Medical Device Regulation (Regulation (EU) 2017/745)
MedTech Europe	European trade association representing the medical technology industries
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
PubMed	Free search engine accessing primarily the MEDLINE database (source: Wikipedia)
SAB	Stakeholders Advisory Board
TD	Technical documentation (of a medical device)
Team-NB	The European Association for Medical devices of Notified Bodies
TL	Task Leader
VDE	Association for Electrical, Electronic & Information Technologies
WHO	World Health Organization
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

Executive Summary

This regulatory compliance monitoring plan describes the planned actions within Task 9.1 of Work Package 9 and their connection to activities in Task 2.2 of Work Package 2.

The goal of T9.1 is to support the partners in the ThrombUS+ project in complying with various legal and regulatory requirements for medical devices. First, this will include the identification of conformity requirements in relevant laws, standards, and guidelines based on the intended purpose and the technical properties as well as the risk characteristic of the ThrombUS+ product. Second, templates for the technical documentation will be created, provided, and their application trained. Third, drafts of regulatory documents will be discussed with partners. Fourth, partners will be trained on selected regulatory topics. Fifth, updates on conformity requirements will be provided during the project time.

1. Introduction

Medical devices for human use are subject to strict legal requirements in Europe to ensure their safety and performance. Primarily, manufacturers must comply with European and national medical device legislation. Due to the respective product characteristics, additional requirements from other areas of law may apply as well (e.g., data protection, radio equipment or disposal of devices and packaging). Moreover, horizontal EU legislation is also applicable for medical devices, e.g. the Artificial Intelligence Act or the Liability Act. In addition, a great number of standards (> 50) and guidelines (> 120) must be considered during medical device development as well.

Taken together, this results in an almost unmanageable number of requirements that necessitate structured and planned implementation. Therefore, a structured and planned process is crucial to ensure the implementation of the resulting number of requirements. Failure to do so poses a major risk that even innovative medical devices with a clear clinical benefit for patients cannot be placed on the market and put into operation.

Task 9.1 “Regulatory compliance monitoring and mitigation activities” aims to support the partners in the ThrombUS+ project in complying with the various legal and regulatory requirements regarding the medical device to be developed. As there is no legal manufacturer in the ThrombUS+ project, the establishment of a quality management system is not part of Task 9.1. Instead, Task 9.1. will mainly focus on the creation of technical documentation (TD) for a medical device. The technical documentation of a medical device is a prerequisite for proving compliance with the regulatory requirements. The organization and structure of a technical documentation are set out in Annexes II and III of MDR.

The following activities in Task 9.1 are essentially planned and are explained in more detail below:

- 1| Identification, collection, evaluation, and summary of applicable legal and regulatory requirements.
- 2| Creation and maintenance of a document structure for the technical documentation.
- 3| Creation, provision, and training of regulatory templates for the technical documentation.
- 4| Preparation of draft documents from templates.
- 5| Distribution of draft documents to project partners for feedback.
- 6| Consideration of the feedback and updates of regulatory documents.
- 7| Knowledge transfer on specific regulatory topics.
- 8| Regular updates of applicable legal and regulatory requirements.

2. Planned Activities

The VDE intends to use all the contacts and sources of information available to provide comprehensive support for the ThrombUS+ project on regulatory issues.

2.1. Identification, collection, evaluation, and summary of applicable legal and regulatory requirements

The respective activities described in this section are carried out mainly in Task 2.2. Based on the intended purpose and the technical properties as well as the risk characteristics of the ThrombUS+ products, relevant laws, standards, and guidelines with conformity requirements will be identified and collected in the [Zotero](#) information database (with access provided to ThrombUS+ partners)¹. The current library is organized in various folders, contains 176 files, including article references, books, guidelines, and legislations (Figure 1).

¹ Application of Zotero is shortly described here: [240126 Zotero literature database.pdf](#).

Figure 1. Current view of the ThrombUS+ Zotero library.
The red rectangle highlights the current folder structure of the library.

In addition, drafts for future legislation are also identified, as early consideration in the technical documentation is recommended.

Among other things, the following sources of information will be used:

- Websites of EU Commission (e.g., EUR-Lex, EUDAMED, MDCG Guidance or AI Watch).
- Databases of national (e.g., DKE or DIN in Germany) and international (e.g., IEC, ISO, IEEE, ETSI, or ITU) standardization bodies.
- Websites of Notified Bodies as well as their national (e.g., IG-NB in Germany) and international (e.g., Team-NB) associations.
- Literature databases (e.g., PubMed, arXiv, or Google Scholar).
- Business social media (e.g., LinkedIn).
- Websites of national and international associations of medical device industry (e.g., MedTech Europe) and partially of medical device industry itself with respect to the analysis of the state of the art.
- Websites of national and international medical associations with respect to medical guidelines (e.g., AWMF).
- Websites of regulatory stakeholders in healthcare (e.g., CAMD, IMDRF, OECD or WHO).
- Standardized internet search queries.
- Newsletters of regulatory stakeholders in healthcare.
- Specialized events with regulatory (related) topics.

Each identified document will be evaluated for content and suitability. Finally, a report with compliance requirements (Deliverable No. 11 - D2.2) will be filed until August 2024, that will serve as reference for the following activities. Moreover, the report will describe an appropriate sequence of regulatory activities and their interactions.

documentation will be prepared that aligns single documents with respective MDR requirements. Partners will be instructed on the application of regulatory templates.

2.4. Preparation of draft documents from templates

Usually, the creation of regulatory documents follows a certain procedure in the pre-market phase as shown in Figure 3. It starts with the installation of the quality management system (not part of the ThrombUS+ project). Then certain processes that build on each other start at various time points. An example is shown in the figure below.

First, the process “Documentation for placing on the market” generates various documents, e.g. dealing with:

- intended use, qualification as and classification of a medical device,
- selection conformity assessment procedure, and
- selection of applicable regulatory requirements from various legislations, standards, guidelines.

Parallel the risk management and the development process start with preparing the risk characteristic, the risk management plan, and the system architecture, respectively. Shortly thereafter in the processes usability (for the product validation activities), clinical evaluation, and post-market surveillance the preparation of respective documents is initiated.

In this work package draft documents based on templates during T2.2 will be prepared by VDE.

Figure 3. Timeline for the regulatory activities during the medical device life cycle.

2.5. Distribution of draft documents to project partners for feedback

The draft documents developed in T2.2 will be distributed to project partners for review. Here, the support of all partners in regulatory tasks will be of crucial importance. This includes both the active contribution of regulatory experience and the provision of technical product information resulting from development activities.

2.6. Consideration of the feedback and updates of regulatory documents

The feedback on regulatory documents by the project partners will be considered. Design changes during development may lead to required changes in the technical documentation. Therefore, updates by project partners are mandatory and the TD must be updated regularly.

2.7. Knowledge transfer on specific regulatory topics

From new technologies (e.g., artificial intelligence) as well as from new legislations, standards, guidelines additional requirements may arise. Therefore, it is important to offer trainings on selected regulatory topics. This will ensure that all partners have the necessary up-to-date regulatory knowledge. For this purpose, online training courses will be scheduled and conducted through MS Teams platform.

2.8. Regular updates of applicable legal and regulatory requirements

Work package 2 will end in December 2024 and the report with compliance requirements will be published already in August 2024. However, the regulatory landscape for medical devices continues to develop until the end of the ThrombUS+ project. Moreover, it is likely that during the development of the ThrombUS+ device design changes occur that will require the consideration of new standards and guidelines. Therefore, the report with compliance requirements will be updated with new documents, if required.